

The role of strategic leadership, organizational commitment, organizational culture, and consensus strategy on the achievements of development strategy plans in Government Agencies in Timor Leste

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Abstract

This research is entitled The Influence of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture Through Consensus Strategy on the Achievement of Development Strategy Plans in Government Agencies in Timor Leste. The purpose of this research is to answer ten hypotheses where hypotheses 1-7 are direct effect hypotheses and three hypotheses are indirect effects. Analysis of the determinant coefficient (R^2), analysis of the influence of power (F_2) and predictive relevance analysis (Q^2) of the measurement model between variables.

The results of the research show that the ten hypotheses are accepted. The results of the R^2 test show that the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the Consensus Strategy is in the strong category. And Consensus Strategy can be explained from Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, and Organizational Culture. The coefficient of determinant variable of Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan belongs to the strong category and has variations which can be explained from Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture and Consensus Strategy. The results of Q^2 for all endogenous variables of the Consensus Strategy and Outcomes of the Development Strategy Plan have very large results and show that exogenous variables have relevance to endogenous variables. The Variable Consensus Strategy has great predictive relevance to the Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan. The results of the F_2 test show that Consensus Strategy has a moderate effect on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan, Organizational Culture has a moderate effect on the Consensus Strategy, and Organizational Culture has a small effect on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan, Organizational Commitment has a small effect on the Consensus Strategy. Strategic Leadership has a small effect on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan and Strategic Leadership has a small effect on the Strategic Consensus.

The conclusions from the test results on the model are able to explain the influence of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture, Consensus Strategy and Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan on government agencies in Timor Leste. It is suggested to the government in Timor Leste to pay attention to, and cultivate Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture, and Consensus Strategy towards the Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan. In this regard, it is necessary to have a government agency or agency at the national level that is responsible for strategic development planning so that it can coordinate and evaluate the achievements of development strategic plans in accordance with the targets set in each government agency in Timor Leste.

Keywords: Strategic Leadership; Organizational Commitment; Organizational Culture; Consensus Strategy; Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan

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1. Introduction

The development strategy plan for Timor Leste was started as an answer to the lofty ideals of independence, namely to achieve a prosperous and prosperous society. As a new country, Timor Leste is carrying out development to achieve the aspirations of the nation and state. the government determines the direction of the next national development by establishing a second long-term development plan known as.

The Strategic Development Plan (PED) of Timor-Leste 2011-2030. The Timor-Leste Strategic Development Plan is a twenty-year vision that reflects the aspirations of the Timorese People regarding the creation of a strong and prosperous Nation. The Plan was developed to inspire change, support bold collective actions and think about a better future.

This Timor Leste Development Strategic Plan (PED 2011-2030) is a twenty-year vision, to reflect the aspirations of the people of Timor Leste in creating a prosperous and prosperous nation.

Handoko (2009) suggests that there are three reasons showing the importance of strategic planning. First, strategic planning provides the basic framework within which all other forms of planning must be adopted. Second, an understanding of strategic planning will make it easier to understand other forms of planning. Third, strategic planning is often the starting point for understanding and evaluating the activities of managers and organizations. Strategic planning is also said to have an important role in ensuring that all members of the organization work towards the same goal.

Researchers define the Consensus Strategy variable as a mediating variable in achieving Timor Leste's long-term development strategy plan by assuming that strategic leadership in top management has the role of strategic consensus and strategic commitment as two dimensions of strategic consensus (Amason, 1996; Dess & Origer, 1987; Wooldridge & Floyd, 1989). The description described by Friend & Hickling (2005, 2012) in Planning Under Pressure makes it clearer that planning will be closely related to politics, otherwise the plan will only become a document that will always be different from reality, or at least the planning will be revised many times. and takes longer. This research is to empirically test and prove the research concept conducted by Ates, Tarakci, Porck, Knippenberg, Groenen, (2020) which states that the correlation between leadershipvisionary and strategic consensus are not significant, test and prove empirically the concept of research conducted by Lestari (2017), that the influence of organizational commitment to strategic plans shows a significant and positive correlation, test and prove empirically the concept of research conducted by Wahyudin, (2022), shows that corporate culture has a significant effect on company performance and tests and proves empirically the research concept of Hunitie's research (2018), which states: strategic leadership significantly predicts that strategic planning and strategic thinking.

2. Methods

In this study there are five variables to be examined, namely the independent variable (X), the mediator variable (Y1), and the dependent variable (Y2). The three classifications of these variables can be explained as follows: Independent variables, namely, Strategic Leadership (X1), Organizational Commitment (X2), and Organization Culture (X3), Intervening variables, namely, Consensus Strategy (Y1) and dependent or dependent variables, namely, Plan Achievements Development Strategy (Y2) in Government Agencies in Timor Leste.

The unit of analysis in this study is the Government Agencies at VIII Governo Constitucional and the samples in this study are leaders and expert staff at state government agencies at five ministries in Timor Leste. The measurement scale used is the semantic differential scale, as said by Riduwan (2013): Very Good/Very Strong/Very Important (7), Good/Strong/Important (6), Good Enough, Strong Enough/Important Enough (5), Moderate/ Normal (4), Fairly Bad/Moderately Weak/Less Important (3), Bad/Weak/Not Important (2), Very Bad/Very Weak/Very Unimportant (1). The measurement model is used to test validity and reliability, while the structural model is used to test causality (testing hypotheses with predictive models). Research data analysis using Smart PLS 4 statistical analysis includes three calculations including algorithms, bootstrapping, and blindfolding. Where is exogenous variable to endogenous variable with direct effect test, indirect effect test and total effect. R Square and R Square Adjusted analyzes were also carried out to find out what percentage of exogenous variables were able to influence endogenous variables.

Figure 1 Research Concept Framework

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Outer Model Measurement

3.1.1. Outer Loading Test, Convergent Validity

The validity test used in this study is convergent validity using the outer loading parameter (reliability indicator) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and discriminant validity using the Fornell-Larcker Criterion parameter. The ideal outer loading respectively

The required item is > 0.708. Table 1 shows that the outer loading variables for Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture, Consensus Strategy and Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan > 0.708. Convergent validity, AVE value > 0.5 (Hair et al., 2017). Based on Table 1, the AVE value for the Strategic Leadership variable is 0.633, the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.702, the Organizational Culture variable is 0.757, the Consensus Strategy variable is 0.734 and the Development Strategy Plan Achievement is 0.729. All variables meet the parameter value of AVE >

0.5. It can be stated that the variables Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture, Consensus Strategy and Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan have good convergent validity.

Table 1 Validity and Reliability Test using Outer Loading, AVE and Composite Reliability

Variabel	Indikator Item	Outer Loading	Average VarianceExtracted (AVE)	Composite Reliability
Strategic Ladership SL (X1)	X1.1	0.777	0.633	0.963
	X1.2	0.848		
	X1.3	0.855		
	X1.4	0.807		
	X1.5	0.749		
	X1.6	0.772		

	X1.7	0.720		
	X1.8	0.761		
	X1.9	0.758		
	X1.10	0.811		
	X1.11	0.751		
	X1.12	0.826		
	X1.13	0.819		
	X1.14	0.835		
	X1.15	0.828		

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

Variabel	Indikator Item	Outer Loading	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Composite Reliability
Organizational Commitment(X2)	X2.1	0.787	0.702	0.963
	X2.2	0.849		
	X2.3	0.839		
	X2.3	0.846		
	X2.4	0.799		
	X2.5	0.835		
	X2.6	0.807		
	X2.7	0.842		
	X2.8	0.867		
	X2.9	0.879		
Organizational Culture(X3)	X2.10	0.856	0.757	0.961
	X3.1	0.874		
	X3.2	0.872		
	X3,3	0.824		
	X3,4	0.882		
	X3.5	0.897		
	X3.6	0.883		
	X3.7	0.859		
Concensus Strategy(Y1)	X3.8	0.864	0.734	0.965
	Y1.1	0.826		
	Y1.2	0.855		
	Y1.3	0.855		
	Y1.4	0.804		
	Y1.5	0.892		
	Y1.6	0.885		
Y1.7	0.875			

	Y1.8	0.844		
	Y1.9	0.830		
	Y1.10	0.898		
Capaian Rencana Strategi Pembangunan (Y2)	Y2.1	0.865	0.729	0.972
	Y2.2	0.848		
	Y2.3	0.863		
	Y2.4	0.890		
	Y2.5	0.899		
	Y2.6	0.842		
	Y2.7	0.840		
	Y2.8	0.829		
	Y2.9	0.810		
	Y2.10	0.864		
	Y2.11	0.847		
Y2.12	0.847			
Y2.13	0.851			

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

3.1.2. Composite Reliability Testing

Reliability testing in this study uses composite reliability. According to Hair et al. (2017), the composite reliability parameter for each variable is > 0.7 . Table 4.4.2a shows that the composite reliability value for the Strategic Leadership variable is 0.963, the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.963, the Organizational Culture variable is 0.961, the Consensus Strategy variable is 0.965 and the Development Strategy Plan Achievement is 0.972. The five variables in this study have fulfilled the parameters of outer loading (loading indicator) and composite reliability. Thus, the variables of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture, Consensus Strategy and Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan can be said to be reliable.

3.1.3. Discriminant Validity Testing

Table 2 Fornell-Larcker Criterion Results

	CRSP	CS	OCu	OCo	SL
CRSP	0.854				
CS	0.930	0.857			
OCu	0.913	0.921	0.870		
OCo	0.890	0.900	0.935	0.838	
SL	0.859	0.861	0.889	0.883	0.795

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

In table 2 for each number in bold is the Fornell Lacker criterion value of each construct. From the table above, it can be seen that the Fornell Lacker criterion value for each construct has the highest value for each latent variable tested with other latent variables, meaning that each indicator can be predicted well by each latent variable and the numbers that are not bolded are the correlation values between constructs with other constructs. Therefore, it can be concluded from the results of tables 1 and 2 that all constructs meet the criteria of discriminant validity.

3.2. Inner Model Testing (Structural Model)

3.2.1. Direct Hypothesis Testing (Direct Effect)

According to Hair et al. (2017), one of the main measurements for evaluating PLS-SEM results is the significance of the path coefficient. In confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), hypotheses test and confirm existing theories and concepts that focus on exogenous variables that are a significant predictor for endogenous variables Structural Model of Influence of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture, and Consensus Strategy on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan.

Table 3 Results of Direct Hypothesis Testing (Direct Effects)

Hypothesis	Path Correlation	Original sample (O)	Standard Deviation(STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P-Values
1	SL > CS	0.141	0.051	2.764	0.006
2	OCo > CS	0.251	0.067	3.751	0.000
3	OCu > CS	0.561	0.058	9.699	0.000
4	CS > CRSP	0.557	0.060	9.259	0.000
5	SL > CRSP	0.114	0.049	2.304	0.021
6	OCo > CRSP	0.140	0.141	4.046	0.000
7	OCu > CRSP	0.298	0.063	4.720	0.000

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

Hypothesis 1

The effect of Strategic Leadership on Consensus Strategy in Timor Leste is (0.141) and significant with a t statistic (2.764 > 1.96) or p-value (0.006 < 0.05). Every change in the Strategic Leadership variable will significantly increase the Consensus Strategy. The H1 hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2

The influence of Organizational Commitment on Consensus Strategy for Government Agencies in Timor Leste is (0.251) and significant with a t statistic (3.751 > 1.96) or p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Every change in the Organizational Commitment variable will significantly improve the Consensus Strategy. Hypothesis H2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3

The influence of Organizational Culture on Consensus Strategy in Government Agencies in Timor Leste is (0.561) and significant with a t statistic (9.699 > 1.96) or p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Every change in the Organizational Culture variable will significantly increase the Consensus Strategy. Hypothesis H3 is accepted.

Hypothesis 4

The influence of the Consensus Strategy on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan in government agencies in Timor Leste is (0.557) and is significant with a t statistic (9.259 > 1.96) or a p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Any change in the Consensus Strategy variable will significantly increase the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan the H4 hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 5

The influence of Strategic Leadership on the Achievement of Development Strategy Plans in government agencies in Timor Leste is (0.114) and significant with a t statistic (2.304 > 1.96) or a p-value (0.021 < 0.05).

Every change in the Strategic Leadership variable will significantly increase the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. Hypothesis H5 is accepted.

Hypothesis 6

The effect of Organizational Commitment on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan in government agencies in Timor Leste is (0.140) and is significant with a t statistic (4.046 > 1.96) or a p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Every change in the Organizational Commitment variable will significantly increase the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. Hypothesis H6 is accepted.

Hypothesis 7

The influence of Organizational Culture on the Achievement of Development Strategy Plans in government agencies in Timor Leste is (0.298) and significant with a t statistic (4.720 > 1.96) or p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Every change in the Organizational Commitment variable will significantly increase the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. Hypothesis H7 is accepted.

Figure 2 Results of the Direct Effect Research Model

3.2.2. Indirect Hypothesis Testing (Indirect Effect)

The mediating variable explains that there are variables that are intervening/intervening in the influence of a variable on other variables. Strategic Leadership is thought to have a direct effect on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan and indirectly (indirect effect) through the Consensus Strategy so that the Consensus Strategy acts as a mediating variable/between the effect of Strategic Leadership on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. The mediation test means whether the Consensus Strategy variable acts as a mediating (intervening) variable for the effect of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. The mediation test can be carried out if the path coefficient of the Consensus Strategy to the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan is significant and the path coefficient of Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture to the Consensus Strategy is significant.

Table 4 Mediation/Indirect Effect Test Results

Hipotesis	Jalur	Original sample(O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P-Values
8	SL -----> CS > CRSP	0.140	0.035	4.046	0.000
9	OCo ---> CS > CRSP	0.312	0.050	6.194	0.000
10	OCu ---> CS > CRSP	0.079	0.032	2.469	0.014

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

Based on table 4 The results of the mediation test above are known as follows:

Hypothesis 8

Consensus Strategy significantly mediates the influence of Strategic Leadership on Strategic Development Planning Achievements in government agencies in Timor Leste by (0.140) and is significant with a t statistic (4.046 > 1.96) or p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Any change in the Consensus Strategy variable will significantly increase the mediating effect of Strategic Leadership on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. Hypothesis H8 is accepted.

Hypothesis 9

Consensus Strategy significantly mediates the influence of Organizational Commitment on the Achievement of Strategic Planning Development Plans in government agencies in Timor Leste by (0.312) and is significant with the t statistic (6.194 > 1.96) or p-value (0.000 < 0.05). Each change in the Consensus Strategy variable will significantly increase the mediation influence of Organizational Commitment on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. Hypothesis H9 is accepted.

Hypothesis 10

Consensus Strategy significantly mediates the influence of Organizational Culture on the Achievement of the Development Planning Strategy in government agencies in Timor Leste by (0.079) and is significant with the t statistic (2.469 > 1.96) or p-value (0.014 < 0.05). Every change in the Consensus Strategy variable will significantly increase the mediation of the influence of Organizational Culture on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. The H10 hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 3 Results of the Indirect Effect Research Model

3.2.3. Total Effect Testing

The results of the test for the total effect of exogenous variables and intervening variables on endogenous variables are as follows:

Table 5 Total Effect/Total Effect

Total Effect		Endogenous Variables	
		CRSP (Y2)	CS (Y1)
Variabel Eksogen	SL (X1)	0.557	
	OCo (X2)	0.611	0.561
	OCu (X3)	0.140	0.251
Variabel Intervening	CS (Y1)	0.192	0.141

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

Based on Table 5 shows the results of the total effect (total effect) between research variables. Strategic Leadership (SL) has a total influence on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan (CRSP) of 0.557 or 55.70%, Organizational Commitment has the largest total influence on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan (CRSP) of 0.611 or 61.10%, and Organizational Commitment has the largest total influence on the Consensus Strategy of 0.561 or 56.10%, Organizational Culture has a total influence on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan (CRSP) of 0.140 or 14.0% and Organizational Culture has a total influence on the Consensus Strategy of 0.251 or 25.10% , The intervening Consensus Strategy variable has a total influence on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan (CRSP) of 0.192 or 19.20%. The total effect results are greater than the direct influence path coefficient indicates the relevance of intervening variables as mediators and the importance of exogenous variables in explaining endogenous variables (Hair et al., 2017). Thus the variables Strategic Leadership (SL), Organizational Commitment, and Organizational Culture are important and require the mediation of a Consensus Strategy in explaining the Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan (CRSP).

3.2.4. Test Results of Model Structure and Predictive Ability

According to Hair et al., (2017) in assessing the structural fit of the model and predictive ability, the measurements used were the R2 (explanation of variance), F2 (effect size), and Q2 (predictive relevance) measures.

Determinant Coefficient Test Results (R2)

There are three categories of grouping on the R square value, namely the strong category, the moderate category, and the weak category (Hair et al., 2011). Hair et al stated that the R square value of 0.75 was included in the strong category, the R square value of 0.50 included the moderate category and the R square value of 0.25 included the weak category (Hair et al., 2011).

The results of the Determinant Coefficient Test (R2) between the Achievement Variables of the Development Strategy Plan and the Consensus Strategy Variables are as follows:

Table 6 R2 Test Results

Variabel Endogen	R-square	R-square adjusted
Capaian Rencana Stretegi Pembangunan (Y2)	0.888	0.887
Consensus Strategy (Y1)	0.864	0.863

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

Based on table 6, the R2 test results show the coefficient of determination test (R2) of the endogenous latent variable in this study. The coefficient of determination of the Consensus Strategy variable is 0.864, so it is classified as a strong category. Consensus Strategy has a variation of 86.4% which can be explained from Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, and Organizational Culture. While the remaining 13.6% is influenced by other variables. The determinant coefficient of the variable achievement of the Development Strategy Plan is 0.888, so it is classified in the strong category (Hair et al., 2011). The achievement of the Development Strategy Plan has a variation of 88.8% which can be explained from Strategic Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture and Consensus Strategy while the remaining 12.2% is influenced by other variables that have not been included in this study.

Effect Size Test Results (F2)

The results of the Effect Size Test (F2) on the Achievement Variables of the Development Strategy Plan, Consensus Strategy, Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment, and Strategic Leadership are as follows:

Based on table 7. shows that the quality of the structural model can be analyzed using an effect test of size f_2 and predictive relevance Q_2 (Hair et al., 2017). The F2 effect size allows assessing the contribution of the exogenous construct value to the endogenous latent variable R2 value. The results of the F2 test show that the Consensus Strategy has a moderate effect or influence on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan (0.396), Organizational Culture has a moderate effect or influence on the Consensus Strategy (0.250), and Organizational Culture has a small effect or low influence on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan. Organizational Commitment has a small effect or low influence on Consensus Strategy (0.053). Strategic Leadership has a small effect or low influence on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan (0.023) and Strategic Leadership has a small effect or low influence on the Strategic Consensus (0.28).

Table 7 F2 Test Results

Variabel	CRSP	CS
Capaian Rencana Stretegy Pembangunan (Y2)		
Consensus Strategy (Y1)	0.396	
Organizational Culture (X3)	0.092	0.250
Organizational Commitment (X2)		0.053
Strategic Leadership (X1)	0.023	0.028

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

Q Square Test Results for Predictive Relevance

The results of the Q Square Test (Q2) on the Achievement Variables of the Development Strategy Plan and the Consensus Strategy are as follows:

Table 8 Q Square Test Results (Q2)

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
Capaian Rencana Stretegy Pembangunan	0.845	0.396	0.291
Consensus Strategy	0.861	0.376	0.260

Source: Primary Data Processing, 2023

Based on table 8. The results of the Q Square test (Q2) show the results of the Q2 test to obtain cross- validated redundancy measurements for each endogenous construct. The resulting Q2 values for all endogenous variables of the Consensus Strategy and Achievements of the Development Strategy Plan are respectively 0.845 or 84.50% and 0.861 or 86.10%, the overall Q2 value has a very large result of 0, indicating that exogenous variables have relevance for endogenous variables. The Variable Consensus Strategy has great predictive relevance to the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan.

4. Conclusion

The findings of this study carry theoretical implications that the Strategic Leadership variable has a significant and positive effect on the Consensus Strategy directly and indirectly influences the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan through the Consensus Strategy mediation variable significantly and positively on strategy translation, strategic intervention, strategic competence, systematic decisions, and control systems in government institutions in Timor Leste. The Organizational Commitment variable has a significant and positive effect on the Consensus Strategy directly and indirectly on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan through the Consensus Strategy variable significantly and positively on inviting members, work patterns, dissemination of vision, work orientation, communication media, training, Standard Operational Procedures, knowledge, identification of resources, involvement of all elements, and Loyalty. The Organizational Culture variable has a significant and positive effect on the Consensus Strategy directly and indirectly on the Achievement of the Development Strategy Plan through the Consensus Strategy mediation variable significantly and positively on Organizational Structure, Organizational Systems, Mission and Strategy, Leadership and Management Effectiveness. Communication and Decision Making, Knowledge and Competence, Innovation and Taking Risks.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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